

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS OF INTERNALLY PRESSURIZED NONCIRCULAR COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

Michael W. Hyer and Gabriela F. Wolford

*Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Blacksburg VA 24061 USA*

ABSTRACT

A progressive failure analysis, based on the capabilities of the finite-element program STAGS, is used to study initial matrix cracking and the subsequent progression of cracking and fiber failure with increased pressure in a small-scale internally-pressurized fiber-reinforced quasi-isotropic elliptical composite cylinder. Primary interest is in determining the pressure necessary to produce a continuous path of failures through the cylinder wall, thereby providing a potential leakage route for the internal pressure. Several failure criteria and various material degradation schemes are used to study path formation due to matrix cracking. It is shown that prior to first fiber failure, matrix cracking alone does not result in a continuous path through the wall of the cylinder. Even though at a particular circumferential and axial location there is considerable cracking, there is always one layer that remains uncracked. The study then turns to fiber failures and the pressure to cause leakage. Illustrated are the patterns of matrix cracking as a function of increased pressure levels, and the pattern of matrix and fiber failures at the pressure that produces leakage.

Keywords: quasi-isotropic lay-up, material degradation, crack progression, first fiber failure, leakage

INTRODUCTION

New concepts for reusable launch vehicles may well include fiber-reinforced composite cylinders as tankage for containing liquid fuels. Because of aerodynamic and structural considerations, tanks with noncircular cross section designs may be used. One of the critical issues to be considered in the design of fiber-reinforced composite tanks is failure due to leakage through the tank's wall. The typical fuels used in these vehicles are gaseous substances such as hydrogen and oxygen that are liquefied at cryogenic temperatures. The internal pressure resulting from these fuels may produce enough matrix cracks in the various layers of the composite material so there is a continuous path for the fuel to escape. This situation, though not catastrophic for the structure, can be extremely hazardous, as it involves leakage of volatile fluids. To prevent this hazard, it is essential that the conditions under which leakage is likely to occur be known. Noncircular cross sections present a particular challenge because the varying radius of curvature with circumferential position can lead to high stresses at specific locations around the circumference. Obviously, with endcaps or domes, boundary conditions at the ends of the cylinders will also cause particular axial locations to have higher stresses than others. The combined effect of axial and circumferential locations of high stress lead to stress concentrations. In ref. 1 the stress concentration effect in cylinders with elliptical cross sections was examined by using a semi-closed form solution to study initial failure, in particular, matrix cracking. Since initial matrix cracking alone does not necessarily result in leakage, the study of failure beyond first failure is necessary. That is the subject of this paper. Specifically, the finite-element code STAGS [2] is used to study the problem by employing a progressive failure analysis. The code is configured to allow for use of a variety of failure criteria and various material degradation schemes to study progressive failure. It is assumed here that leakage will occur if at some circumferential and axial location within the cylinder, there is failure in

Figure 1 Problem description, nomenclature, and geometry of elliptical cylinder

every layer of the cylinder wall, thereby providing a leakage path. In the context of finite elements, it is assumed that leakage will occur if for a particular element, every layer of material is damaged.

The paper first examines if due to matrix cracking alone, leakage will occur. The maximum stress, Hashin, and Tsai-Wu failure criteria and various degradation schemes are used in this portion of the study. As will be seen, up to first fiber failure, though there is considerable cracking at specific circumferential and axial locations, there is always one layer that remains uncracked at those locations, thereby preventing leakage. Interest then turns to considering pressure beyond the level to cause first fiber failure to the level to cause leakage. Here only the maximum stress failure criterion and just one material degradation scheme are employed.

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

The problem considered consists of the elliptical cylinder described in fig. 1 with $2a$, $2b$, and L denoting, respectively, the major diameter, minor diameter, and length of the cylinder reference surface. The crown and keel denote the upper and lower flatter parts of the cylinder, and the sides the more curved portions. The circumference of the reference surface is denoted by C . The degree of ellipticity, e , is defined here as the ratio, b/a . The wall thickness of the cylinder is denoted by H and the internal pressure by p_o . Spatial locations axially are denoted by x , with $x=0$ at the cylinder midspan and $-L/2 \leq x \leq L/2$. The circumferential coordinate is s , where $s=0$ at the top of the cylinder and $-C/2 \leq s \leq C/2$. The axial, circumferential, and normal components of displacement of the reference surface are given by u^o , v^o , and w^o , respectively. It will be assumed that each end of the cylinder is clamped to a rigid end plate or bulkhead which can move axially. Accordingly, clamped boundary conditions are applied to each end of the cylinder, with the exception of allowing the end at $x=+L/2$ to move uniformly in the axial direction to accommodate the pressure-induced axial motion. The end at $x=-L/2$ cannot move axially in order to restrict rigid body movements. The quasi-isotropic laminate considered has a layup sequence of $[\pm 45/0/90]_8$, where 0° is the axial direction. Eight layers is a reasonable number from the point of view of manufacturing small-scale cylinders by hand on an elliptical mandrel for initial experimental work. In that context, the length considered is 12.5 in., $2a=10$ in., $2b=7$ in., resulting in $e=0.7$.

Figure 2 Finite-element model of elliptical cylinder with various mesh densities along length

The finite-element model is constructed of 3500 elements using the STAGS 410 element, a plane stress element. The mesh spacing is uniform in the circumferential direction, but has increased density in the axial direction near the clamp ends. The finite-element mesh is shown in fig. 2.

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS SCHEME

The failure criteria considered here are the maximum stress criterion, the Hashin criterion, and the Tsai-Wu criterion. All three criteria rely on knowing the failure stresses for the basic failure modes. Those basic modes and the notation used herein follow the notation used in STAGS and are given by:

X_t = tensile failure stress in fiber direction

X_c = compressive failure stress in fiber direction (a positive number)

Y_t = tensile failure stress transverse to fiber direction

Y_c = compressive failure stress transverse to fiber direction (a positive number)

S_{xy} = inplane shear failure stress

The operative equations for maximum stress failure criterion then become:

$$\frac{\sigma_1}{X_t} = 1; \quad \frac{\sigma_1}{X_c} = -1; \quad \frac{\sigma_2}{Y_t} = 1; \quad \frac{\sigma_2}{Y_c} = -1; \quad \frac{|\tau_{12}|}{S_{xy}} = 1 \quad (1)$$

for fiber tensile and compression, matrix tensile and compression, and inplane shear failure, respectively. For the Hashin criterion, the operative equations become:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{xy}}\right)^2 = 1; \quad \frac{\sigma_1}{X_c} = -1;$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{xy}}\right)^2 = 1; \quad \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{2S_{xy}}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_c}{2S_{xy}}\right)^2 - 1\right]\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_c} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{xy}}\right)^2 = 1; \quad \frac{|\tau_{12}|}{S_{xy}} = 1 \quad (2)$$

for fiber tensile and compression, matrix tensile and compression, and inplane shear failure, respectively. The Tsai-Wu failure criterion can be expressed as:

$$F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + F_{66}\tau_{12}^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

where

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{X_t} - \frac{1}{X_c}; \quad F_2 = \frac{1}{Y_t} - \frac{1}{Y_c}; \quad F_{11} = \frac{1}{X_t X_c}; \quad F_{22} = \frac{1}{Y_t Y_c}; \quad F_{12} = -2\sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}}; \quad F_{66} = \frac{1}{S_{xy}^2} \quad (4)$$

With the maximum stress and Hashin criteria, the mode of failure is determined by which equation of each criterion equals unity. For the Tsai-Wu criterion, the failure modes are determined as follows: Fiber or matrix or inplane shear failure is assumed to occur when the following terms, respectively, dominate:

$$F_1\sigma_1 + F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2, \text{ or } F_2\sigma_2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2, \text{ or } F_{66}\tau_{12}^2.$$

In the above, the numerical subscripts 1, 2, and 12 denote the stresses in the principal material coordinate system, a standard notation in the mechanics of composite materials. The assumed values of the failure stresses for a layer of graphite-epoxy are taken to be

$$X_t = 200, \quad X_c = 180, \quad Y_t = 7.25, \quad Y_c = 29, \quad S_{xy} = 14.5 \text{ ksi} \quad (5)$$

and the engineering properties are assumed to be

$$E_1 = 18.85 \text{ msi}, \quad E_2 = 1.407 \text{ msi}, \quad G_{12} = 0.725 \text{ msi}, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.300, \quad h = 0.0055 \text{ in.} \quad (6)$$

The values above are representative of a medium modulus graphite-epoxy material.

The material degradation schemes used here can be summarized as follows: The pressure is increased from zero in 10 psi increments. At each pressure step the stresses are computed and one of the failure criteria above is applied at each integration point in each layer in each element. The degradation scheme, identified as DGRAD2 in STAGS, does the following: For failure due to σ_2 , either tension or compression, the engineering properties E_2 , G_{12} , and ν_{12} , or just E_2 and ν_{12} , depending on user preference, are multiplied by a factor of β , $\beta \leq 1$, and the ratio of ν_{12} and the minor Poisson's ratio, ν_{21} , is fixed at the ratio for the undegraded material. For failure due to excessive inplane shear stress, G_{12} is multiplied by the factor β . For failure due to excess stress in the fiber direction, E_1 , G_{12} , and ν_{12} are multiplied by the factor β , and the ratio of ν_{12} and ν_{21} is fixed at the ratio for the undegraded material. The equilibrium conditions with the degraded, or reduced, engineering properties are then recomputed at that pressure and the stresses recalculated to determine if, due to stress redistribution, more failure results. Generally this is the case, so the engineering properties within the layers and elements with additional failures are reduced, and the analysis is repeated. This procedure continues until failure at the particular pressure stops, i.e., a converged solution occurs. The pressure is then increased and the process repeated. The result is a map of the failure locations within the cylinder wall at various pressure levels. In the analysis here, there are eight integration points per layer per element, so with an eight-layer laminate, there are 64 integration points per element that are checked for failure and the possible reduction of engineering properties.

Figure 3 Method of illustrating one quadrant of cylinder in three dimensions

RESULTS

To investigate and illustrate the predicted layer failure scenarios, the pictorial method illustrated in fig. 3 is used. The quadrant of the cylinder defined by the axial range $0 \leq x/L \leq 0.5$ and the circumferential range $-0.25 \leq s/C \leq 0.25$ is isolated from the rest of the cylinder (see fig. 1). That quadrant is then flattened and the thickness coordinate is greatly exaggerated. The thickness coordinate is redefined to be ζ , which is measured from the midwall location, and is nondimensionalized by H . The thickness range is then $-0.5 \leq \zeta/H \leq 0.5$. With this, the quadrant is represented in three-space and the individual layers in the thickness direction can be identified. Layer 1, the inner $+45^\circ$ layer, is at the bottom. For the analysis, the finite elements and the layers making up the elements fill this three-space. When a matrix failure due to σ_2 is detected at any integration point within a layer, the failure is noted in the two-dimensional rendering of three-space by putting a small circle at the x - s - ζ centroidal location of that layer. Square symbols denote failure due to excessive σ_1 and triangular symbols denote failures due to excessive inplane shear stress τ_{12} . Though there are eight integration points per layer per element that can fail, due to the limited resolution of the three-dimensional rendering of fig. 3, the exact location of each integration point is not identified. As the pressure is increased from the level for initial cracking, more and more circles are added to the three-space and the pattern of cracking becomes evident. It is important to note that due to the existence of the bending stiffnesses D_{16} and D_{26} , there is not quarter-symmetry in the response. However, displaying the results for just one quadrant can be used to make important points and the displays are somewhat simplified.

Maximum stress failure criterion

The left column of fig. 4 is a map of the failure locations within the quadrant of the quasi-isotropic cylinder at four pressure levels, starting at 140 psi, based on the maximum stress failure criterion and a reduction of E_2 , G_{12} , and ν_{12} by a factor of $\beta = 0.2$. This will be considered the baseline case for this paper. As can be seen, at 140 psi there are matrix failures in two elements in the inner $+45^\circ$ layer. These failures, and all to follow, are due to excessive tensile values of σ_2 and are thus cracks through which leakage could occur. Note that these first failures occur at the end of the cylinder ($x/L=0.5$) at a value of $s/C \approx -0.12$ to -0.15 , not at a location of cross sectional symmetry, i.e., not at $s/C = 0$ or

degrade E_2 and G_{12} , $\beta=0.2$
(baseline)

degrade only E_2 , $\beta=0.2$

degrade E_2 and G_{12} , $\beta=0.05$

140 psi

170 psi

200 psi

230 psi

Figure 4 Crack locations, maximum stress criterion: baseline and variations

± 0.25 . The location of the first crack is determined by the stress concentration effect, which is a function of the noncircular geometry and the layup. There are not companion failures at positive values of s/C because of the aforementioned non-zero values of D_{16} and D_{26} . There are, however, companion failures at $s/C > 0.25$ (the lower quadrant at that end of the cylinder) and at the other end of the cylinder ($x/L=0$). At 170 psi, there is more cracking in the inner layer, cracking in layer 2, a -45° layer, and isolated cracks in layers 5 and 8. It is hard to detect, but the cracking in layer 1 is progressing axially away from the cylinder end. This is evidenced by the fattening of the circles in layer 1, which is really the effect of circles plotted at locations $x/L < 0.5$ partially obscuring the circles plotted at $x/L=0.5$. At 200 psi there is further cracking of layers 1 and 2, the cracking in those layers almost overlapping,

additional cracking in layers 5 and 8, and cracking in layers 4 and 7. At 230 psi the cracking in layers 1 and 2 overlap and further extend axially away from the cylinder ends. There is even more cracking in layers 4 and 5 and 7 and 8, but no cracking in layers 3 and 6, which are 0° layers. As there are no cracks in the 0° layers, it must be that the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° layers are reacting the hoop stress resultant due to the internal pressure. Fiber failure occurred at approximately 246 psi. It can be observed that cracks are accumulating near (not at) the ends of the major diameter in several layers.

The middle column of fig. 4 illustrates the effect of changes in the engineering property degradation scheme relative to the baseline case, where it is assumed that E_2 and ν_{12} , but not G_{12} , are multiplied by a factor of $\beta = 0.2$ when cracking is detected. Relative to the baseline case, this reflects how important the shear modulus G_{12} is in resisting further cracking. As can be seen, relative to the baseline case, it is difficult to see any differences in the crack maps, implying that G_{12} is not important for resisting matrix crack progression.

The right column of crack maps in fig. 4 provides another engineering property degradation scenario within the context of the maximum stress failure criterion. This is for the case of reducing E_2 , G_{12} , and ν_{12} using the value of $\beta = 0.05$. Though the reduction in engineering properties is severe, to within the resolution of the figures, there is no difference in this failure scenario relative to the baseline case. The computer run time for the case of $\beta = 0.05$ was noticeable longer than for the cases with $\beta = 0.2$.

Hashin and Tsai-Wu failure criteria

As seen above, the variations of the engineering property degradation within the context of the maximum stress failure criterion had little influence on the matrix cracking scenario. This section explores the influence of using different failure criteria. Figure 5 shows the crack maps for the baseline case in the left column, for the Hashin criterion in the middle column, and for the Tsai-Wu criterion in the right column. With the Hashin criterion E_2 , G_{12} , and ν_{12} are reduced using the value of $\beta = 0.2$, same as with the baseline case. As can be seen, at 140 psi there are more matrix cracks predicted by the Hashin criterion than by the baseline case. However, the region of the cylinder where the first failures are predicted to occur are the same as for the baseline case. At 170 psi the Hashin criterion again predicts more matrix cracks than the baseline case, but with a similar distribution of crack locations. At the 200 psi pressure level the matrix crack distributions of the Hashin criterion and the baseline case are similar. The Hashin criterion predicts more cracks, but not significantly more. Finally, at 230 psi the predicted matrix crack distributions look remarkably similar. To be noted, however, is more overlapping of the cracked regions in layers 1 and 2, and the fact that at whatever location the cracks are predicted to exist, the Hashin criterion always predicts more cracks at that location. Because the Hashin criterion allows for an interaction between stress components τ_{12} and σ_2 , matrix cracks will initiate at a lower pressure than for the maximum stress criterion, and there will be more cracks predicted at a given pressure. Interestingly, though the presence of τ_{12} influences the number of cracks predicted, degrading or not degrading the value of G_{12} didn't seem to be important when using the maximum stress criterion, as the left and middle columns of fig. 4 showed. The first fiber failure pressure predicted by the Hashin failure criterion is 246 psi, same as the maximum stress failure criterion.

Predictions made using the Tsai-Wu criterion are based on using a factor $\beta = 0.2$. For the Tsai-Wu criterion, STAGS is configured so that only E_2 and ν_{12} are degraded when matrix cracking due to a tensile value of σ_2 is detected. More precisely, then, the predictions of the Tsai-Wu criterion should be compared with the middle column of fig. 4. However, since the results in that column are almost identical to the baseline results, it is not an important point. It can be observed that at 140 psi more cracks are predicted to occur with the Tsai-Wu criterion than for the maximum stress criterion. This is like the Hashin criterion predictions, but a careful look at the crack maps show that the initial cracking based

degrade E_2 and G_{12} , $\beta=0.2$
(baseline)

Hashin, degrade E_2 and G_{12} , $\beta=0.2$ Tsai-Wu, degrade E_2 , $\beta=0.2$

140 psi

170 psi

200 psi

230 psi

Figure 5 Crack locations: comparisons among maximum stress, Hashin, and Tsai-Wu criteria

on the Tsai-Wu criterion does not occur in exactly the same elements as predicted by the Hashin criterion. At 170 psi, the Tsai-Wu criterion predicts more crack propagation axially away from the end than the maximum stress criterion predicts. This is clearly evident at 200 psi, where the Tsai-Wu criterion predicts significant crack propagation away from the ends, particularly in inner layers 1 and 2, and particularly near the ends of the major diameter in layers 7 and 8. Fiber failure is predicted by the Tsai-Wu criterion to occur at 216 psi, so that matrix crack map at 230 psi is not shown.

For all cases considered in figs. 4 and 5, at least one layer remains uncracked at first fiber failure. Thus no leakage predicted.

PRESSURE INCREASE TO PRODUCE FIRST FIBER FAILURE AND LEAKAGE

Since the results of the previous section indicate that up to first fiber failure leakage is not predicted to occur, the question immediately arises as to what level of fiber failure, with possible accompanying matrix cracking, is necessary to cause leakage. Are large amounts of fiber failure required to have leakage? Or is only a small amount beyond the first fiber failure all that is necessary? To answer these questions, the baseline maximum stress criterion is used to predict failure results beyond first fiber failure to the point of having leakage. Figure 6 summarizes the results from the pressure to cause first matrix failure to the pressure to cause leakage for the quasi-isotropic cylinder. The cracking maps at 140 and 200 psi illustrated earlier are included, now using red to denote tensile failure due to σ_2 . Fiber failure occurs at 246 psi, and it can be observed that at that pressure there is considerable matrix cracking in the inner two layers, with accumulations near the ends of the major diameter, and in layers 7 and 8, also with accumulations near the ends of the major diameter. To a lesser degree there is matrix cracking near the ends of the major diameter in layers 4 and 5. Note, however, there are no cracks in layers 3 and 6, 0 deg. layers. At just a slightly greater pressure, namely at 260 psi, there is a significant change in the type of damage that occurs. In addition to the matrix cracks due to σ_2 , layers 1, 2, 7, and 8 develop matrix compression failure, layers 2 and 3 develop fiber tensile failure, layers 6 and 8 develop fiber compression failure, and layers 3-8 develop cracks due to excess inplane shear stresses. Taken together, these different modes of failure combine to allow leakage in the region of $s/C=-0.15$. It is interesting that inplane shear failures and material crushing due to compressive values of σ_1 and σ_2 were not issues at the lower pressures.

SUMMARY

In summary, it is seen that for the problem considered, the maximum stress failure criterion shows little sensitivity to the variations in elastic property degradation schemes investigated. The variations are felt to represent a realistic range of possible degradation effects. It can also be concluded that for this particular problem, the maximum stress and Hashin criteria predict very similar results. The Tsai-Wu criterion, on the other hand, predicts significantly more cracking, though a similar cracking pattern, and a lower first fiber failure pressure. Interestingly, however, for all situations studied here, there are two layers that exhibit no matrix cracks at first fiber failure, and thus there is no leakage path through the cylinder wall. An increase in pressure from 246 to 260 psi is all that is required to produce leakage. This is due to a combination of matrix failures and failures in the fiber direction. A close look at fig. 6, however, shows that at 260 psi the inplane shear failures and the matrix failures combine so there is a crack in every layer in a particular element, thereby leading to leakage. Failures in the fiber direction are not really necessary to cause leakage. However, the inplane shear failures occur in conjunction with the fiber failures due to the mechanics of the stress redistribution, so it is really a mute point to talk about inplane shear failures without failures in the fiber direction.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work reported on herein was supported by grant NAG-1-01072 from the Mechanics and Durability Branch of the NASA-Langley Research Center to Virginia Tech. The authors sincerely appreciate the financial support. The NASA grant monitor was Dr. Damodar Ambur. The authors would also like to thank Dr. Norman F. Knight, Jr., of Veridian Systems Div. for valuable help with various aspects of STAGS.

REFERENCES

1. McMurray, J.M. and M.W. Hyer, "Response and Failure Characteristics of Internally Pressurized Elliptical Composite Cylinders," *AIAA Journal*, Vol 40, No 1, 2002, pp. 117-125.
2. Rankin, C.C., F.A. Brogan, W.A. Loden, and H.D. Cabiness, "STAGS Users Manual, Version 3.0," Lockheed-Martin Missiles & Space Co., Inc., Report LMSC P032594, March 1999

Figure 6 Failure locations for quasi-isotropic cylinder at various pressures